

PROFESSIONAL HONOR, ADVANTAGES, REPUTATION OF MEDICAL STAFFS AND LEGAL ASPECTS OF THEIR PROTECTION

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Abstract. *The article provides legislative and regulatory acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan on medical and social protection of doctors and medical personnel. As well as the results of a survey to study medical and social problems among 1267 doctors and indications for identifying emotional burnout were studied among 329 medical workers.*

Keywords: *dignity of doctors, emotional burnout, professional reputation, legislative and regulatory acts.*

Relevance. Recently, there has been an increase in the number of offenses related to belittling the honor and dignity of medical workers on the part of patients. However, often due to legal illiteracy and/or reluctance to waste time on proceedings of this kind, doctors do not apply to the authorities and do not try to defend their legal rights to protect honor, dignity and professional reputation.

Unfortunately, such an attitude leads to undesirable consequences, such as a decrease in the authority of the medical specialty and disappointment in one's own profession. Today, there are cases of tense relationships between doctor and patient, which leads to conflicts and sometimes bodily harm. It is the doctor's duty to understand the cause of the disease and try to eliminate it. From this point of view, the medical worker is sometimes forced to communicate with the patient for a long time. On the part of the patient, one can often observe a consumerist, boorish attitude towards the doctor, aggressive behavior and manifestations of disrespect of varying degrees. Many doctors believe that they only have a duty and no rights. However, from the point of view of jurisprudence, such a conclusion is fundamentally incorrect. Despite the fact that doctors do not have a special legal status, they are also citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, therefore, they have equal constitutional rights with all citizens.

This dissertation research to a certain extent contributes to the implementation of the tasks specified in the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № DP-5590 "On comprehensive measures to radically improve the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated December 7, 2018, №. DP-6110 "On measures to introduce fundamentally new mechanisms in the activities of primary health care institutions and further improving the efficiency of reforms carried out in the health care system" dated November 12, 2020, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №. PO-5038 "On organizing the activities of the agency for the development of medical and social services of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated 25 March 2021, as well as in other regulatory legal documents in this area.

Purpose of the research. Study of legislative and regulatory acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan on medical and social protection of doctors and medical personnel.

Methods of the research. The study used a random sampling method, analytical, questionnaire, expert evaluation, and statistical analysis method.

Results of the research. A survey was conducted to study medical and social problems among 1267 doctors (using the example of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the city of Tashkent and the Samarkand region), indications for identifying emotional burnout were studied among 329 medical workers (213 doctors and 116 nurses), the allocation of preferential vouchers for health improvement in a sanatorium (Republic of Karakalpakstan, Tashkent city and Tashkent region).

Do you experience difficulties in performing daily loads (functional tasks) on your part? We received the following answer from respondents. According to the results of the analysis, 632 (50%) respondents answered that there were no difficulties in carrying out the load, and 584 (46%) answered that it was difficult to carry out the load, because she's big.

In order to determine the level of emotional burnout among medical staffs and their use in modern information and communication technologies, a mobile website and a telegram bot channel have been developed. In this case, you enter the program by phone or computer using a link on a mobile website or in a telegram, enter your phone number, last name, first and last name, specialty, work experience, and everyone passes a 21-question test. This, in turn, made it possible to quickly determine the level of psycho-emotional burnout among medical workers.

As a result of a study of the number of allocated preferential vouchers for medical personnel, it was revealed that in 2018 - 2153, in 2019 - 2373 and in 2020 - 1086. In 2019, the number of allocated preferential vouchers increased by 9% compared to 2018, and in 2020 year, their number decreased by 50% compared to 2018. It is assumed that this, in turn, was due to the fact that quarantine was declared in 2020 due to the coronavirus pandemic in the country and the closure of many institutions, including sanatoriums.

It is important that the protection of the rights and dignity of medical workers begins with higher medical educational institutions and is accompanied by continuous training in short-term courses. The Center for Independent Medical Expertise under the Association of Doctors of Uzbekistan works to protect the dignity of doctors. Its charter and procedure for conducting the examination were approved. Today, the Center cooperates with the Russian Medical Chamber, where several of its specialists were trained at short-term training seminars. According to the analysis, in 2017–2021, the Center for Independent Expertise provided consultations to doctors in various areas, including injuries to doctors received by patients or their relatives, insults, disclosure of medical confidentiality, and the quality of medical services. Based on the work program “Requirements of current legislation in this area” in order to improve the knowledge and skills of future doctors in the field of medical law in higher educational institutions of the sixth year of the Department of Public Health. Healthcare management of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute among undergraduate students (research group) and for 2nd year master's students (control group) for the first time, a 6-hour training was conducted on the topics: “Relationships between doctors and patients. Legislation and regulations. Algorithms for actions in case of insults to medical personnel.” In total, 298 respondents took part in the educational process, including 121 bachelor’s students and 168 master’s students. To determine the results of assimilation, pre- and post-testing was used, i.e. test with a total of 32 questions, on two topics and 3-5 answer options for each question.

Conclusion. When studying the workload of physicians, 584 (46%) of the total number of respondents reported difficulty in performing the workload and noted the size of the workload. The presence, size and complexity of the load can lead to medical errors. Reducing the syndrome

of psycho-emotional burnout among doctors, preventing conflicts with patients, allows you to take the right actions in conflict situations and increase the efficiency of medical care.

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